

Significance of the addition and deduction in accounting

by **Md. Israr Hassan Khan**, *Professor & Head,*
P.G. Centre of Commerce,
Sri Arvind Mahila College, Kazipur, Patna - 800004
&
Shreya Kumari, *Research Scholar,*
P.G. Department of Commerce
Email : kshreya918@gmail.com

Abstract :

This article shows the significance of addition and deduction in accounting. Addition (revenues and assets) and deduction (expenses and liabilities) are two important components of accounting.

Addition represented by credits where deduction represented by debits. By analyzing real-world examples and case studies, the article provides a deeper understanding how addition and deduction plays an important role in determining the financial position of a business and how it helps to create a base of reliable financial information for business and organizations.

Keywords : Accounting, addition, deduction, revenues, assets, expenses, liabilities.

1. Introduction :

Accounting is the fundamental aspect of managing the financial aspect of any organization. It is not only the statistical procedure for the collection, classification,

and summarization of financial information but also the analytical and interpretation of book-keeping records. It is a regular and most systematic procedure, to know the business result with minimum trouble. It is also the preparation of financial and economic information, which involves the measurement of transactions and other events relating to the entity. It serves as the language of business, helping decision-makers make informed choices and ensuring compliance with financial regulations. It is semi analytical in nature.

Deduction means a process of subtracting allowable expenses or reduction from the gross income of a business or individual in order to determine the taxable income. It can significantly impact the amount of tax owed, reducing the overall tax liability and potentially providing tax incentives for certain activities or investments. Accurate and proper documentation of deduction is essential to comply with tax laws and regulations.

In accounting “addition” is not a specific concept like deduction. It is a process of including income, revenue or other financial inflows into the financial records of a business or individuals. It’s essential for calculating totals, verifying balances, and determining the overall financial health of a business.

2. Objectives of the study :

This research is deeply understanding about the significance of addition and deduction in accounting and finding an alternative to traditional method of accounting.

➤ *The significance of addition in accounting :*

1. **Revenue Recognition :** Addition in accounting primarily refers to recognizing revenues. Revenue is the lifeblood of any business and correctly identifying and recording it is important. This includes sales revenue, interest income, and any other income generated by the organization.
2. **Assets Accumulation :** When a company acquires assets, such as property, equipment or investments, it is considered as addition to its balance-sheet. These additions can have a long-term impact on the organization’s financial health.

3. Growth and Expansion : Addition of profits and assets often reflects the growth and expansion of a business. It's a positive indicator of a company's performance and can attract investors and stakeholders.

➤ *The significance of deduction in accounting :*

- 1. Expense Recognition :** Deduction in accounting is related to recognizing expenses. This involves recording costs associated with running the business, such as employee salaries, rent, utilities and other operating expenses. Proper expense deduction is important for accurate financial reporting.
- 2. Liabilities :** Deduction can also include the recognition of liabilities, such as loans payable and outstanding obligations. These represent financial commitments that the organization needs to fulfill in the future.
- 3. Profit Calculation :** Deduction play a crucial role in calculating the net profit of a company.

By subtracting expenses and liabilities from revenue and assets, organizations can determine their true profitability.

Balancing Act in Accounting :

Accounting is a delicate balancing act between addition and deduction. The ultimate goal of an organization is to maintain a positive balance. When addition (revenue and assets) exceeds deduction (expenses and liabilities); a company generates a profit, if deduction is more than addition it shows a loss of a company.

Conclusion :

Addition and deduction are the pillars of accounting. They are essential for understanding a company's financial health, decision making, and reporting to stakeholders. Accurate and transparent accounting practices are important for any organization, as they enable it to thrive, grow and make informed financial decisions properly managed addition and deduction in accounting. The method of addition and deduction can prove to be a revolutionary step in the world of accountancy and bring a more transparent vision of company records.

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